

Enhancing the ability to write poetry and creative thinking skills with rural nature-inspired contextual approach

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ABSTRACT

There are still many students who face difficulty in expressing ideas for writing poetry, and not a few students are less motivated in writing literary works in the kind of poetry. The aim of this study was to analyze the effect of learning with a rural nature-inspired contextual approach on the ability to write poetry and creative thinking skills of elementary school students. Quasi-experimental study is used in this study with a non-equivalent pre-test post-test control group design. The research population was all fifth-grade students, totaling 231 students. The sample was taken by random sampling technique, totaling 44 students. Data were collected using a test technique. The test instruments were in the form of a description test and a five-scale non-test instrument. Both instruments have been analyzed for their feasibility quality by testing their validity and reliability. The data analysis technique used MANOVA with the help of SPSS. The results showed that the significance value of the MANOVA test results was 0.000 (<0.0). It means that there is a difference in both partial and simultaneous studies in writing poetry and students' creative thinking skills who learn by applying a contextual approach inspired by rural nature. So, there is a positive effect of learning with a rural nature-inspired contextual approach on the ability to write poetry and creative thinking skills.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Writing ability is one of the four skill components found in Indonesian language subjects. Writing ability involves the abilities of children cognitive in the form of actualized ideas in a series of arranged words in symbols and writing [1]. Writing activity can explore thoughts and feelings about an object, choose what things to write, and write it down so that the reader can easily understand it clearly. Writing activities are basically to give birth to thoughts and feelings and express ideas, knowledge, knowledge, and experiences of one's life in written language. Writing skills are related to students' literacy skills [2]. In addition, students' writing skills will affect success in the learning process [3], [4]. As a result, writing is not a simple activity that can be learned, but rather must be mastered.

One of the productive and expressive writing activities is writing literature. Literature is a beautiful work. The beauty of literature lies in the pleasant expression of language. Literature is a human creation in spoken and written language that can create a good feeling [5], [6]. Literary learning is in the form of literary appreciation learning and literary expression learning. There are two kinds of literary expression learning, namely oral expression and written expression. The purpose of learning written literary expression is for

students to express their experiences in written literature. Another goal of learning literary expression is for students to have a passion for writing literary works to increase knowledge and use it in daily activities [7], [8]. In this case, students have honed their sensitivity to the environment and can express it in written essays, both in prose and poetry.

Writing poetry is a writing activity to pour his experiences into written language by choosing aesthetic value words. In writing poetry, a writer must continue to learn and practice to give a valuable impression to his readers [9]. Writing poetry emphasizes students' skills in exploring language forms that are carried out in an aesthetic corridor to express ideas, ideas, and feelings through implicit ways [10]. Writing poetry cannot be separated from the writer's imagination [11], [12]. Writing poetry helps students develop writing skills and can encourage students to articulate more complex emotions to produce experiences [11]. Writing poetry can help students develop creative thinking skills in both language and writing [13], [14]. Writing poetry supports the development of confidence and communication skills [15]. So, writing poetry provides wider opportunities for students to develop critical thinking and creative thinking skills. The process of writing poetry is inseparable from the ability to think creatively. Critical thinking skills become one of the skills that have to be possessed in the 21st century. Higher-order thinking skills including analysis, testing, communication problem solving, and scientific process skills are all part of creative thinking. [16]. Flexibility and fluency are required for creative thinking [17], novelty, and elaboration [18], [19]. Divergent and convergent thinking skills are types of thinking skills [20], [21]. Creative thinking skills are very necessary in the improvement of students, especially in writing poetry. Creative thinking skills are needed to produce a creative work of poetry. It is enhanced by previous research that states that creative thinking improves poetry writing skills [12].

So, it can be said that the students' writing ability plays a role in their learning process. Ability of students in writing is affected by how the students use written language effectively. This will be realized if students develop strong basic language skills [22]. Therefore, to realize this, learning must facilitate chances for students to improve their writing skills. The teacher's role in designing learning is very much needed. Especially in designing learning, the process of designing learning requires innovative and creative methods. Learning to write has long been implemented with various methods, but there has been no optimal result in learning to write until now. There are still many obstacles in learning to write in schools. They tend to be avoided as obstacles in writing, including the limited time allocation available, minimal facilities and infrastructure, student interest is still low in writing poetry. Indonesian language lessons are placed at the last hour. It does not promote the process of learning. This condition is supported by the initial analysis results that researcher with fifth-grade students have carried out. It is known that many students face challenges in writing poetry, are less motivated to participate in writing class because the learning provided by the teacher is very conventional (only strong on the material) and run monotonously without any variation in the methods or learning techniques provided. If this condition is not addressed, it will undoubtedly have a significant impact on students' writing abilities.

In general, learning to write poetry in these classes is still low. When participating in poetry writing lessons, students still find it difficult to find ideas or inspiration. The low ability of students in writing poetry is due to the lack of effective learning created by the teacher. The ineffectiveness is due to the lack of precise strategies applied by the teacher in learning. The strategy used by the teacher cannot develop the potential that exists in students so that students can freely express their feelings. It is because Indonesian language learning is still done traditionally, teachers still use the lecture method in delivery and lack of motivation and ways of teachers to increase students' creative thinking skills. In addition, the low ability of students to write poetry is also due to the lack of variety of teachers in developing learning media and methods used. If this is ignored, of course, it will not have a good impact on writing poetry and the ability to think creatively.

One possible solution to solve this problem is to apply a learning model. This solution has been widely carried out, stating that there is an innovative learning model. According to previous research learning to write poetry using the student team achievement divisions (STAD) model can significantly increase students' poetry writing skills [8]. Research states that the picture model is more effective and interesting for students than the second model of imaginary suggestions in fostering interest in writing poetry and literary texts [16]. Research states that applying the literary workshop model can improve the quality of the process and students' poetry writing skills [11]. Research on students' ability to write poetry in literary works using inquiry techniques, exercises, and guidance has increased learning and changed students' behavior towards writing interest which is quite significant [23]. The research states. According to the findings of this study, the acquisition of student scores using the think-pair-share (TPS) type cooperative strategy has increased [24]. Research states that the Synectic model effectively improves writing skills [25]. This description illustrates that learning with an innovative learning model will positively influence the ability to write poetry. For this reason, one of the solutions offered in this study is to use a contextual teaching and learning (CTL) approach.

The CTL approach is a learning concept that helps students to make connections between their knowledge and its application in their lives by assisting teachers in relating the material being taught to students' real-world situations. The existence of a CTL approach will provide opportunities for students to play an active and participative in a role. It makes learning with a contextual approach more meaningful. Of course, meaningful learning like this will provide experiences for students to use in everyday life and develop students' social-emotional abilities [26], [27]. Therefore, the contextual learning approach is very well used to hone students' creative thinking skills [28], [29], improve motivation, learning outcomes [30], [31].

This statement follows the research results, stating that the CTL learning model affects student outcomes [31]. Research states that using the CTL approach to mathematics learning outcomes in fractional addition arithmetic operations has increased both quantity and quality [32]. Research states that the CTL approach effectively improves reading comprehension and student motivation [33]. Previous research found that the CTL model application can increase students' ability in writing poetry [13]. So, the existence of CTL will have a positive impact on the result of learning, motivation, and creativity of students in the process of learning. One of the solutions proposed related to learning approach is the use of learning media.

Learning media are tools or intermediaries that can facilitate the process of learning to streamline interaction between teachers and students [34]. The presence of learning media will enhance the learning environment. One of the media that is often used in elementary schools is environmental-based media. The material provides in environment is an excellent learning tool. Even as it is non-purchasable materials such as trees, river water, grass, air, sunlight, and so on [35]. Environment-based media is a learning strategy that applies the environment as learning objectives, learning resources, and learning tools [36]. This environmental media is more concrete, and students can observe for themselves, students will easily get inspiration [37]. So, the existence of the environment will provide opportunities for students to get to know the environment around them. The integration of environmental-based learning is important for education. Students are more concerned and take care of this natural environment, which can improve learning outcomes [38].

Base on several studies that have been carried out previously regarding to environment-based learning include research which states that environmental-based learning has an effect of 29.1% on environmental care behavior [39]. Research states there are a significant differences in science knowledge competence between groups of students who taught with the discovery learning model assisted by environmental media and groups of students taught using conventional learning [40]. Research that states the use of environmental-based media has a positive and significant influence on learning outcomes [37], [41]. So, the existence of environmental media will greatly help students in the learning process because of what is found in concrete. It follows the learning media that must be used in elementary schools where students are still in the concrete operational stage.

These descriptions illustrate that using the CTL approach and the environment will affect learning outcomes. CTL learning inspired by the rural natural environment is carried out. This research is different from those that already exist because no previous research on CTL has not been integrated with the rural natural environment. The existing research is still very minimal in examining how CTL integrates with the rural natural environment for the variables of poetry writing ability and creative thinking ability. A research objective was formulated to analyze the impact of learning with a rural nature-inspired contextual approach on the learning outcomes of writing poetry and elementary school students' creative thinking skill. Applying the CTL approach inspired by rural nature will allow students to develop inspiration in writing poetry. With inspiration, students can see a real picture or situation. It will provide meaningful experiences for students to use in everyday life to realize meaningful learning.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study was used a quasi-experimental research design with a non-equivalent pre-test post-test control group design. In this study, there were two groups: the experimental group, which was taught using the CTL approach inspired by rural nature. And the control group, which was taught using the conventional learning model. Both research groups will be given a pre-test and post-test to determine the difference in the scores of poetries writing skills and students' creative thinking skills. At the beginning and after the treatment was given.

The population of this study was all fifth-grade students in Cluster V, Sukasada District, Indonesia which consisted of nine schools with 231 students. The samples were collected using a random sampling technique after population distribution was done. After the equivalence test with the ANOVA test was conducted, it was found that the classes were equivalent. Then the class was randomized to determine the experimental class and the control class. The experimental class obtained was 22 students, and the control class was 22 students. The experimental class follows the lesson by applying a project assessment based on national insight, and the control class follows the lesson by applying a conventional assessment.

The data collection method used is a description test, which requires students to create a literary work, in this case, poetry. This test consists of one question, which is C6. Completing this test instrument is equipped with the grid shown in Table 1. In addition to the test instrument, the ability to think creatively is measured by non-test. The non-test instrument consists of five aspects which will be developed into 30 statements. The complete instrument notes grid is described in Table 2. The items developed were then tested for validity and reliability with the content validity ratio (CVR) test. The CVR results reveal that of the 30 statement items developed, 30 were declared valid with a score of 0.71-1. Meanwhile, for the reliability test, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. Critical thinking skills will also be observed from the poetry produced by looking at aspects of Aptitude Traits' creative thinking skills including originality, elaboration, fluency, and flexibility [42].

The pre-test data obtained were analyzed descriptively using the T-test. MANOVA test were used in descriptive analysis and inferential analysis of the post-test data. The prerequisite tests were completed prior to the MANOVA test namely normality, homogeneity, and multicorrelation. Both the MANOVA test and test prerequisite were conducted with SPSS 25.0 for Windows.

Table 1. The poetry writing ability

Dimension	Indicator
Diction	The ability to accurately distinguish the nuances of meaning following the idea to be conveyed The ability to find a form that fits the situation and values the taste exactly according to it
Imagination	Imaginary images, thought images, mental impressions, or visual images and the language that describes them
Concrete words	Describing a painting of a state or inner mood to evoke the reader's imagination
Figurative language	Figurative language makes the content more beautiful. It means emitting many meanings or words of meaning in the dictionary of literary terms
Verification	Verification includes rhythm, rhyme, and meter
Typography	First distinction that can be seen in differentiate poetry from prose fiction and drama.
Means of rhetoric	Rhetoric is a trick of the mind. This <i>Muslimat</i> /moslem woman mind is in the form of language that continues to invite readers to think

Table 2. Creative thinking skills

Dimension	Indicator	Statement	
		Positive	Negative
Non-aptitude traits			
Curiosity	Students pay attention to the teacher's explanation	1	1
	Students will ask the teacher if they find problems related to the material given	1	1
	Students will seek clearer information related to writing poetry	1	1
	Students will answer questions posed by the teacher	1	1
	Students don't just use textbooks to complete assigned tasks	1	1
Imaginative	Students can write poetry that is different from the existing ones according to their imagination	1	1
	Students can see the errors of sentences that compose poetry	1	1
Feeling challenged	students will feel challenged to complete the task of composing poetry	1	1
	Students never give up on completing the task of writing poetry	1	1
	Students work individually on the assigned task	1	1
Dare to take risks	Students keep trying until the given task can be completed on time	1	1
	Students remain confident in the poetry that is made	1	1
	Students Dare to accept difficult assignments related to writing poetry	1	1
Appreciate	Optimistic about the correctness of the completed answer	1	1
	Students consider the opinions of friends, teachers to complete the work done	1	1
Total		15	15

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study analyzes the contextual approach inspired by rural nature on writing poetry and students' creative thinking skills. This research has obtained the expected results: a rural nature-inspired contextual approach to learning is influenced. The results of the descriptive analysis in detail are described in Table 3. The next test was the prerequisite test for the pre-test data group, for both data on the ability to write poetry and students' creative thinking ability. The Kolmogorov Smirnov statistic is use in the normality, the results of the pre-test data both poetry writing ability and creative thinking ability data which were normally distributed (Sig.>0.05) with a score of 0.186 for learning outcomes and 0.164 for creative thinking ability scores. The homogeneity test become the second prerequisite test conducted. The homogeneity test results of the ability to write poetry and think creatively come from a homogeneous data group indicated by (Sig.>0.05) which is 0.853 for the ability to write poetry and 0.743 for the ability to think creative. Based on the prerequisite test, writing poetry and creative thinking obtain from a normal and homogeneous distribution

then continue to independent t-test. The t-test result showed a score (sig.>0.05) a score resulting 0.655 for the ability to write poetry and 0.353 for the creative thinking ability of students. It reveals that both of the group did not differ because of the sig.>0.05.

Table 3. Descriptive analysis of metacognitive abilities and learning outcomes results

		Descriptive statistics			
Treatment		Dependent variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
A1 (Experimental)	Pre-test	Y ₁	88.86	4.40	22
		Y ₂	86.81	3.30	22
	Post-test	Y ₁	84.63	5.40	22
		Y ₂	83.09	5.90	22
A2 (Control)	Pre-test	Y ₁	84.09	4.17	22
		Y ₂	85.59	4.67	22
	Post-test	Y ₁	85.81	4.10	22
		Y ₂	82.59	3.76	22

The normality test with Kolmogorov-Smirnov become the first prerequisite test. The analysis results show that all data come from normally distributed data groups. The Sig score indicate it >0.05. Table 4 displays the findings of a comprehensive analysis. The homogeneity test is the next prerequisite test after the normality requirements have been met. The homogeneity test was performed in this study using two analyses: i) The homogeneity test with Levene's test of equality; and ii) The homogeneity test with box's test of equality of covariance matrices. The homogeneity analysis' result carried out show the same meaning. The research data comes from homogeneous data groups, as seen from the sig score. Each test showed a value of more than 0.05. Score Sig. Levene's test of equality test is 0.115 for learning result, while the score of Sig. creative thinking ability of 0.119. Meanwhile, the homogeneity test using box's test of covariance matrices yielded a F score of 2.514 with Sig. 0.056. The next prerequisite test is a multicorrelation test where this test has purpose to determine the relationship between each variable being analyzed.

Table 4. Normality analysis test result

		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		
Learning approaches		Statistic	df	Sig.
Poetry writing skills	Contextual approach learning inspired by rural nature	0.180	22	0.061
	Conventional learning	0.145	22	0.200
Creative thinking skills	Contextual approach learning inspired by rural nature	0.081	22	0.200
	Conventional Learning	0.164	22	0.129

The prerequisite test for the MANOVA analysis has been meet. The obtained research data are normally distributed, homogeneous, and there is no multicorrelation between variables, allowing hypothesis testing with MANOVA to be performed. The complete analysis is described in Table 5 and Table 6.

Several findings were drawn from the analysis results. First, the MANOVA results reveal Pillai trace, Wilks' lambda Hotelling's trace, and Roy's largest root, showing that the F coefficient is 4.308 with a Sig score. 0.020 This implies a concurrent difference in the ability to write poetry and think creatively between groups of students who take lessons with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature and groups of students who take lessons using conventional learning. Second, the tests of between-subjects effects analysis results show an F score of 4.427 with Sig. 0.041, which is smaller than 0.05. It means a significant effect of learning with a rural nature-inspired contextual approach on writing poetry. Third, the tests of between-subjects effects analysis results showed an F score of 8.026 with Sig. 0.007, which is smaller than 0.05. It means a significant learning effect with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature on students' creative thinking abilities.

Table 5. Results of multivariate analysis

Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	
Intercept	Pillai's trace	0.998	9175.672	2.000	41.000	0.000
	Wilks' lambda	0.002	9175.672	2.000	41.000	0.000
	Hotelling's trace	447.594	9175.672	2.000	41.000	0.000
	Roy's largest root	447.594	9175.672	2.000	41.000	0.000
	Pillai's trace	0.174	4.308	2.000	41.000	0.020
Learning approaches	Wilks' lambda	0.826	4.308	2.000	41.000	0.020
	Hotelling's trace	0.210	4.308	2.000	41.000	0.020
	Roy's largest root	0.210	4.308	2.000	41.000	0.020

Table 6. Tests of between-subjects effects

Source	Dependent variable	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	Poetry writing skills	102.023	1	102.023	4.427	0.041
	Creative thinking skills	196.568	1	196.568	8.026	0.007
Intercept	Poetry writing skills	335651.114	1	335651.114	14565.427	0.000
	Creative thinking skills	315693.841	1	315693.841	12890.588	0.000
Learning approaches	Poetry writing skills	102.023	1	102.023	4.427	0.041
	Creative thinking skills	196.568	1	196.568	8.026	0.007
Error	Poetry writing skills	967.864	42	23.044		
	Creative thinking skills	1028.591	42	24.490		
Total	Poetry writing skills	336721.000	44			
	Creative thinking skills	316919.000	44			
Corrected total	Poetry writing skills	1069.886	43			
	Creative thinking skills	1225.159	43			

Based on the analysis results, the first finding shows a simultaneous difference in the ability to writing poetry and the ability to think creatively between experimental and control group. Learning activities in the experimental class refer to the stages of a contextual approach by combining them with the rural natural environment. CTL learning is one approach that provides opportunities for students to get to know problems that exist in the real world. Learning that emphasizes what is experienced by students in everyday life will be more meaningful for elementary school students. It is considering that elementary school children are still in the actual operational phase. Children who have a concrete operational phase still need the help of real/concrete learning media because elementary school children are not yet able to think abstractly [43], [44]. CTL learning and the media of the rural natural environment will make students learn well because the CTL is a learning concept that assists teachers in relating the material being taught to students' real-world situations and help them to make connections between their knowledge and its application in their lives such as family members and members of the public. Learning with a contextual approach gives the chance for students to be active, independent, and responsible in the process of learning. So, CTL learning inspired by rural nature will increase student motivation in the learning process, especially learning to write poetry. The existence of rural natural media will make students find more ideas or ideas that can be used to produce a work of poetry. Writing poetry inspired by what they find will make learning more fun, and this will undoubtedly improve the learning environment. so that the goals of learning can be realized.

The existence of CTL learning inspired by rural nature will make students gain hands-on experience in writing poetry. Writing poetry is a writing activity to pour his experiences into written language by choosing aesthetic value words. In writing poetry, a writer must continue to learn and practice to give a valuable impression to his readers [12]. Writing poetry emphasizes students' skills in exploring language forms that are carried out in an aesthetic corridor to express ideas, ideas, and feelings through implicit ways. Writing poetry cannot be separated from the writer's imagination [45]. Writing poetry helps students develop writing skills and can encourage students to articulate more complex emotions to produce experiences [11]. Writing poetry can support students to improve creative thinking skills in both languages and writing [13], [14], writing poetry help to grow confidence and communication ability of students [15]. So, the ability to write poetry will help students to develop writing skills.

Writing activity can explore thoughts and feelings about an object, choose what things to write about, and write it down so that the reader can easily understand it clearly. It expresses a person's ideas, knowledge, knowledge, and life experiences in written language. Writing skills are related to students' literacy skills [2]. In addition, students' writing skills will affect success in the learning process [3], [46]. With good writing skills, students will be able to communicate their opinions regarding the material being studied, and good writing skills will make students understand better what they are learning. Writing is not only how to express imagination but also relates to how students can express and collaborate their imaginations with ideas or ideas that follow the theme of the poem that they want to be sincere.

The development of creative thinking skills will accompany the development of students' writing skills. It is because in writing a poem, students must think convergent and divergently. The ability of students to think convergent and divergently is known as creative thinking ability. The ability to think creatively in learning to write poetry is very important to note [13], [47]. The ability and ability of a person's creative thinking (poet) in writing poetry will appear in the results of his writings. Learning that trains creative thinking skills will certainly affect the formation of students [48], [49]. So, it can be said that students who have good writing skills will also have good creative thinking skills. In other words, the ability to write has a relationship with the ability to think creatively. This statement is supported by several research results stating that writing skills will be much better if students have creative thinking skills [47]. Research states a positive

and significant relationship between creative thinking and writing skills. There is a simultaneous difference in the ability to write poetry and think creatively between students who take lessons with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature and groups of students who take lessons using traditional learning.

The second finding is a great impact of learning with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature on the poetry writing ability of fifth-grade elementary school students. The difference in the ability to write poetry obtained by students who take part in learning by applying a rural nature-inspired contextual approach with students which learning by applying conventional learning. It is because the learning process that applies a rural nature-inspired contextual approach provides opportunities for students to be active in the process of learning, they will gain more experience. In other words, learning with the CTL model will create meaningful learning. Meaningful learning will occur when students obtain experience and able to develop emotional intelligence while the learning process is conducted using a constructivism approach [27], [50]. Children can obtain experience through problem-solving activities or activities conducted with a scientific process. The learning process results in evidence in the form of social experiences.

CTL learning, besides making students active in writing poetry, in the learning that students do, students will also improve their poetry writing skills. CTL learning inspired by rural nature provides opportunities for students to develop poetry writing skills such as aspects of students' diction, which can be seen in the ability to accurately distinguish nuances and meanings according to the ideas to be conveyed and the ability to find forms that are appropriate to the situation and the value of feeling is appropriate to the situation. It can also be seen from the titles and writings of students. With a rural natural atmosphere, students can develop poetry ideas. Students can increase their imagination by looking at the rural natural environment, which will increase their imagination by seeing the real conditions they encounter. This environmental media is more concrete, and students can observe for themselves, students will easily get inspiration [51]. The concept that was developed again was concrete words, indicating that students develop in describing a figurative state or mood. It is closely related to the learning carried out, namely CTL with the environment and developing the aspect of language style, which shows that, on average, students use the right language style so that the language style expresses a meaning. So, it can be said that a rural nature-inspired contextual approach is appropriate implement to fifth-grade elementary school students in poetry writing skills.

The third finding shows a significant effect of learning with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature on the creative thinking ability of fifth-grade elementary school students. Of course, this difference results from the learning process carried out. The contextual learning process is inspired by rural nature, which emphasizes real-world-based learning will provide many learning experiences. Contextual learning inspired by rural nature develops the idea that working alone, discovering oneself, and constructing new knowledge and skills will help children learn more meaningfully [52]. CTL learning support students to create connection between the knowledge they have and their application in life.

In contrast, students gain knowledge gradually and through the process of self-construction as a means of solving problems in their lives [32]. So, CTL learning emphasizes more on the learning process by fully involving students in the process of learning. It is following learning to write poetry that uses a learning process using a contextual approach inspired by rural nature. In writing a poem, students are challenged to be able to make good poetry. The ability of students to imagine, express ideas is strongly influenced by how students think critically.

Critical thinking skills become one of important skill that must be owned in the 21st century. Higher-order thinking skills such as analysis, testing, communication problem solving, and scientific process skills are all part of creative thinking [16]. Creative thinking involves flexibility, fluency [17], novelty, and elaboration [18], [19]. Thinking ability consists of divergent and convergent thinking skills [20], [21]. Creative thinking skills are very necessary in the improvement of students, especially in writing poetry. Creative thinking skills are needed to produce a creative work of poetry. Creative thinking skills will be well-formed if they are accustomed or trained by giving problems from their daily lives that make the learning process more meaningful. Based on this result, it is possible to state that learning with a contextual approach is inspired by rural nature is appropriate for fifth-grade elementary school students in improving students creative thinking abilities.

Another finding obtained in the learning process is that the CTL learning process provides great chance for students to interact with peers. Learning that involves peers will have a good impact on the formation of children's character. A good relationship between peers will be very effective in attracting children's interest in the learning process. Learning with peers support students to take an active role in their process of learning [53], [54]. The peer method improves self-learning. Students go through experiences that are feedback from their friends [55]. Peers assist and guide each other in developing learning through interaction and collaboration [56]. The existence of peers helps, guides, and supports peers to create learning opportunities through collaboration and interaction [56]. Peer-to-peer learning reduces anxiety and stress. Students' self-confidence will grow as they are guided, assisted, and given feedback by their peers [57], [58].

Based on these descriptions, learning must allow students to share learning expectations to create conducive learning and follow current conditions.

An essential finding in this study is the positive effect of a rural nature-inspired contextual approach on poetry writing and students' creative thinking skills. Learning with the inspiration of rural nature has changed learning that was originally Learning shifts from teacher-centered to student-centered. The teacher only serves as a facilitator and mediator in the learning process. Students actively carry out the learning process by making poetry, discussing, developing creative thinking skills, and sharing experiences. The teacher has a role as a motivator and facilitator of student learning activities in the learning process. The difference in creative thinking abilities obtained by students who take part in learning by applying learning with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature and students who take part in by applying traditional learning is due to differences in treatment in learning activities. Learning activities in the experimental class belongs to the stages of the contextual approach. The contextual approach inspired by rural nature allows students to be more independent and responsible in the process of learning and further hone students' skill related to creative thinking. For example, on assignments students are given the freedom to express their ideas. So that students' attitudes in learning can be developed. Assignments makes students allows to comprehend, apply, investigate, and share their knowledge.

4. CONCLUSION

Learning with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature can affect writing poetry and students' creative thinking skills. Learning with a contextual approach inspired by rural nature allows students to learn actively without any coercion from the teacher. Students learn to work together and work together with their peers to reduce the burden in the learning process. In addition, students can freely pour ideas in their heads to train their creative thinking skills in this learning.

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